

Thermodynamic Parameters for the Cleavage of Esters by Hydrobromic Acid

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The influence of temperature on the rates of cleavage of diethyl esters of malonic acid, succinic acid, glutaric acid and phthalic acid by hydrobromic acid in pure acetic acid and binary mixtures of acetic acid with toluene, carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene has been studied. The thermodynamic parameters for the reaction have been calculated.

THE kinetics of cleavage of esters by halogen hydracids in acetic acid and in mixed solvents has been reported earlier^{1,2} and the reaction has been found to be a second order one, first order with respect to the substrate and first order with respect to the nucleophile. The effect of temperature on the cleavage rate has now been thoroughly investigated.

Experimental

The solvents used were purified by the usual procedure and freshly distilled before use. The substrates were of guaranteed grade from Fluka.

The physical constants of the purified materials are: Acetic acid b.p. 118°; nD^{20} 1.3683, toluene b.p. 116.6°; nD^{20} 1.496, carbon tetrachloride b.p. 76.5°; nD^{20} 1.461, nitrobenzene b.p. 211°; nD^{20} 1.553, diethyl malonate b.p. 197°; nD^{20} 1.4143, diethyl succinate b.p. 218° nD^{20} 1.4208, diethyl glutarate

b.p. 233.7°; nD^{20} 1.4241, diethyl phthalate b.p. 282°; nD^{20} 1.1515.

Hydrobromic acid used was a freshly distilled azeotropic mixture (b.p. 126°).

The kinetics was followed by the usual argentimetric procedure (Volhard's method).

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constants ($\times 10^3$ l.moles⁻¹ min⁻¹) for the first step of cleavage of diethyl malonate, diethyl succinate, diethyl glutarate and diethyl phthalate by hydrobromic acid in 100% acetic acid and 70 : 30 (v/v) mixtures of acetic acid with toluene, carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene at 60°, 70° and 80° are tabulated in tables 1-4.

Plots of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ were all linear. The thermodynamic parameters—energy of activation (ΔE), frequency factor (PZ), entropy of activation (ΔS)

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE CLEAVAGE OF DIETHYL ESTERS BY HYDROBROMIC ACID IN 100% ACETIC ACID

Esters	Concentration of		$k_1 \times 10^3$ l.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹		
	ester	HBr	60°	70°	80°
Diethyl malonate	0.05035 M	0.0518 M	1.778	3.758	6.273
Diethyl succinate	0.04903 M	0.0546 M	1.1	2.4	4.445
Diethyl glutarate	0.04986 M	0.0542 M	0.8465	1.8	3.610
Diethyl phthalate	0.04991 M	0.0537 M	0.6341	1.4	2.912

TABLE 2—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE CLEAVAGE OF DIETHYL ESTERS BY HYDROBROMIC ACID IN 70 : 30 (v/v) ACETIC ACID—TOLUENE MIXTURE

Esters	Concentration of		$k_1 \times 10^3$ l.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹		
	ester	HBr	60°	70°	80°
Diethyl malonate	0.0505 M	0.0515 M	5.8	15.0	30.50
Diethyl succinate	0.0528 M	0.0502 M	4.2	11.22	27.78
Diethyl glutarate	0.0525 M	0.0505 M	3.3	9.12	24.69
Diethyl phthalate	0.04998M	0.04992M	2.9	5.9	18.25

TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE CLEAVAGE OF DIETHYL ESTERS BY HYDROBROMIC ACID IN 70 : 30 (v/v) ACETIC ACID—CARBON TETRACHLORIDE MIXTURE

Esters	Concentration of		$k_1 \times 10^3$ l.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹		
	ester	HBr	60°	70°	80°
Diethyl malonate	0.04897M	0.04986M	2.82	6.5	16.26
Diethyl succinate	0.0517 M	0.0506 M	1.8	4.4	—
Diethyl glutarate	0.05225M	0.0518 M	1.66	3.8	15.15
Diethyl phthalate	0.05008M	0.04994M	0.96	2.4	8.2

TABLE 4—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE CLEAVAGE OF DIETHYL ESTERS BY HYDROBROMIC ACID IN 70 : 30 (v/v) ACETIC ACID—NITROBENZENE MIXTURE

Esters	Concentration of		$k_1 \times 10^3$ l.moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹		
	ester	HBr	60°	70°	80°
Diethyl malonate	0.04898M	0.04992M	1.03	2.24	5.38
Diethyl succinate	0.04909M	0.0505 M	0.8	1.55	3.4
Diethyl glutarate	0.05126M	0.0518 M	0.36	1.26	2.87
Diethyl phthalate	0.0528 M	0.05225M	0.28	0.79	2.03

and enthalpy of activation (ΔH)—for the cleavage of these esters have been calculated and reported in tables 5–8. It will be seen that the parameters are quite in accordance with the bimolecular processes.

TABLE 5

Solvent : 100% acetic acid

Esters	ΔE K.Cals/ mole	PZ	$-\Delta S$ e.u.	ΔH K.Cals/ mole
Diethyl malonate	17.7	8.17×10^7	22.4	17.0
Diethyl succinate	18.4	3.34×10^6	28.8	17.7
Diethyl glutarate	17.1	6.46×10^5	32.1	16.4
Diethyl phthalate	23.3	5.33×10^9	14.6	22.6

TABLE 6

Solvent : 70% acetic acid—30% toluene (v/v)

Esters	ΔE K.Cals/ mole	PZ	$-\Delta S$ e.u.	ΔH K.Cals/ mole
Diethyl malonate	19.2	1.48×10^8	21.3	18.5
Diethyl succinate	21.7	6.62×10^9	14.2	21.0
Diethyl glutarate	23.0	4.27×10^{10}	10.1	22.3
Diethyl phthalate	21.4	5.75×10^8	14.1	20.7

TABLE 7

Solvent : 70% acetic acid—30% carbon tetrachloride (v/v)

Esters	ΔE K.Cals/ mole	PZ	$-\Delta S$ e.u.	ΔH K.Cals/ mole
Diethyl malonate	25.2	1.55×10^{12}	3.1	24.5
Diethyl glutarate	25.6	2.82×10^{12}	1.9	24.9
Diethyl phthalate	27.9	1.38×10^{12}	3.3	27.2

TABLE 8

Solvent : 70% acetic acid—30% nitrobenzene (v/v)

Esters	ΔE K.Cals/ mole	PZ	$-\Delta S$ e.u.	ΔH K.Cals/ mole
Diethyl malonate	20.0	2.69×10^7	24.7	19.3
Diethyl succinate	24.0	1.48×10^{10}	12.8	23.3
Diethyl glutarate	22.5	1.70×10^9	16.5	21.8
Diethyl phthalate	21.4	5.37×10^8	18.8	20.7

The small frequency factor is probably due to the process involving fairly complex molecules with large number of degree of freedom.

ΔH and ΔS vary in such a helter-skelter fashion, that isokinetic relationship suggested by Leffler and Grunwald³ fails. A plot of ΔH versus ΔS gives a scattered pattern. The absence of correlation cannot be attributed to experimental uncertainty. Such results have been reported in the formation of oximes⁴, thiosemicarbazones⁵, guanlylhydrazones⁶ and in studies on ester hydrolysis in 85% ethanol-water (v/v)⁷. The failure of the relationship in the present investigation may be due to the structural changes encroaching closely on the reaction zone. Or, it is probable that the patternless scatter is due to the observations being made at temperatures near the isokinetic temperature⁸.

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VISVANATHAN : THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

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